

August 2, 2020

ICFA announces a new phase towards preparation for the International Linear Collider

At its 86th meeting held today, ICFA approved the formation of the International Linear Collider International Development Team as the first step towards the preparatory phase of the ILC project, with a mandate to make preparations for the ILC Pre-Lab in Japan.

A description of the mandate and structure of the ILC International Development Team was also approved by ICFA today.

The Team will commence its work immediately and is expected to complete it by the end of 2021.

The ILC International Development Team will work towards making a timely realization of the ILC possible.

ICFA thanks the Linear Collider Collaboration led by Dr. Lyn Evans for its excellent work over the past several years.

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